

1 **Transcriptomic discovery in HCV.**

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6 We established an RNA-sequencing based method for study of HCV infection at the systems level in
7 Huh7.5 human cells infected with HCV genotype 1b. We demonstrate here silencing of the protein kinase
8 DNA-activated catalytic subunit *Prkdc* in cells following HCV infection. PRKDC silencing during Hepatitis C
9 infection was accompanied by loss or repression of nuclear or transcriptional factors *Mycn* and *Lin28b*
10 despite activation of *Jun*.

11 Citations

12 1. Ferguson, B.J., Mansur, D.S., Peters, N.E., Ren, H. and Smith, G.L., 2012. DNA-PK is a DNA
13 sensor for IRF-3-dependent innate immunity. *elife*, 1, p.e00047.

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